

TO STUDY THE PREVALENCE OF CARPAL TUNNEL SYNDROME, ITS SEVERITY AND FUNCTIONAL STATUS AMONG HAIRDRESSERS IN TWIN CITIES OF PAKISTAN: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

Dr. Abdul Haseeb¹, Dr. Asia Manzoor², Dr. Maheen Shakeel³, Dr. Zowaina Kanwal⁴,
Dr. Safina Malik⁵, Dr. Ehtisham Ijaz⁶, Dr. Sardar Salman Javed⁷

¹Department of Physical Therapy, Zohra Institute of Health Sciences Rawalpindi, House Officer Fauji Foundation Hospital Rawalpindi.

²Doctor of Physical Therapy, Zohra Institute of Health Sciences Rawalpindi. Consultant Physiotherapist at Zohra Nursing Home, Rwp.

³Department of Physical Therapy, Zohra Institute of Health Sciences Rawalpindi. Consultant Physiotherapist at Zohra Nursing Home Rwp.

⁴Department of Physical Therapy, Zohra Institute of Health Sciences Rawalpindi. House Officer ISLAMABAD MEDICAL COMPLEX (NESCOM).

⁵Department of Physical Therapy, Zohra Institute of Health and Sciences Rawalpindi, House Officer Islamabad Medical Complex (NESCOM).

⁶Doctor of Physical Therapy, Iqra University Chak Shahzad Campus Islamabad.

⁷Doctor of Physical Therapy, Zohra Institute of Health Sciences Rwp. Lecturer at Munawar Institute of Medical Sciences Rwp.

¹seebicious@gmail.com, ²asiamalik6088@gmail.com, ³imaheenahmed@gmail.com, ⁴zowainak@gmail.com

⁵maliksafina016@gmail.com, ⁶ehtishamijaz2002@gmail.com, ⁷javedsalman36@gmail.com

Corresponding Authors:*

DOI:

Received
22 July, 2025

Accepted
23 August, 2025

Published
26 August, 2025

ABSTRACT

Research Topic: To study the prevalence of carpal tunnel syndrome, its severity and functional status among hairdressers in twin cities of Pakistan: A cross-sectional study. Background: Carpal Tunnel Syndrome (CTS) is a common occupational disorder caused by repetitive hand movements and prolonged wrist positions. Hairdressers are particularly at risk due to the nature of their work. This study aimed to determine the prevalence of CTS among hairdressers in the twin cities of Pakistan and to assess its impact on their functional activities. Aims and Objectives: The main aim of this study was to determine the prevalence of Carpal Tunnel Syndrome (CTS) among hairdressers in the twin cities of Pakistan and to identify how many hairdressers are affected by CTS in twin cities. Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted with 385 hairdressers from Rawalpindi and Islamabad. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire based on symptom severity and functional status, including hand pain, numbness, tingling, and difficulty in daily tasks such as writing, buttoning, and gripping objects. Data Analysis: The data collected from 385 hairdressers through structured questionnaires were entered and analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic data, such as age, gender, work experience, and working hours. Results: The prevalence of CTS among participants was found to be 11.9%, while 88.1% were classified as normal. Most participants were aged between 37–47 years and had 5–15 years of working experience. Although the majority reported mild or no symptoms, a notable number experienced pain, numbness, or functional limitations, particularly during repetitive tasks or at night.

Conclusions: CTS is present in a significant portion of the hairdressing population, highlighting the need for awareness, ergonomic interventions, and preventive strategies in this profession. Early detection and proper management may help reduce long-term disability and improve work productivity.

Keywords: Carpal Tunnel Syndrome, Prevalence, Severity, Functional Status, Hairdressers (Pakistan)

INTRODUCTION

Carpal Tunnel Syndrome (CTS) is one of the most common hand conditions caused by compression of the median nerve as it passes through the carpal tunnel of the wrist. The carpal tunnel is a narrow, rigid passageway formed by bones and ligaments on the palm side of the hand. When swelling or irritation occurs within this space, it compresses the median nerve, resulting in symptoms such as numbness, tingling, weakness, and pain in the thumb, index, and middle fingers. If untreated, CTS can progress from discomfort to long-term disability, significantly impairing work performance and quality of life (Alessia Genova et al., 2020).

CTS is often associated with repetitive hand movements, forceful exertion, awkward wrist positions, and prolonged physical strain. Occupational groups such as assembly workers, food processors, barbers, and drillers are particularly vulnerable. Non-occupational risk factors also play a role, including obesity, pregnancy, diabetes, rheumatoid arthritis, and genetic predisposition (Aboonq, 2015; Agnessa Kozak et al., 2015). Studies suggest that both environmental and biological factors interact to increase the risk, making CTS a multifactorial disorder.

Anatomically, the carpal tunnel is formed by the carpal bones and the flexor retinaculum, containing the median nerve and flexor tendons. The median nerve is especially vulnerable at two sites: the proximal edge of the tunnel and its narrowest part near the hook of the hamate. Compression in these regions impairs vascular supply, disrupts the blood-nerve barrier, and causes inflammatory changes, leading to ischemic nerve injury and chronic dysfunction (Alessia Genova et al., 2020).

The clinical presentation of CTS progresses through stages. Initially, patients experience night-time symptoms such as tingling, numbness, or pain radiating to the forearm and shoulder. These often improve with hand movement but recur with repetitive tasks during the day. As the condition worsens, patients may develop weakness, clumsiness, and loss of grip strength, while severe cases show

muscle wasting of the thenar eminence (Sanjoy K Gupta & Timothy J Benstead, 1997). Diagnosis commonly relies on physical examination tests like Phalen's test, Tinel's sign, and median nerve compression (Durkan, 1991).

Treatment strategies vary according to severity. Conservative approaches include ergonomic modifications, splinting, physiotherapy, and medications. Physical therapy emphasizes pain reduction, improved movement, tendon gliding, and strengthening exercises, often supported by neurodynamic testing. Modalities such as ultrasound, infrared radiation, laser therapy, and Transcutaneous Electrical Nerve Stimulation (TENS) are also applied to reduce symptoms (Bobowik, 2019; Huisstede et al., 2018). Complementary therapies, including acupuncture, yoga, and massage, have shown additional benefits. Surgical decompression, however, remains the definitive treatment for severe CTS (Carlson et al., 2010).

From a public health perspective, CTS is a major occupational health issue. It is one of the most prevalent musculoskeletal disorders among working-age individuals and a leading cause of lost productivity and absenteeism. Research highlights that high repetition of tasks is a stronger predictor of CTS than high force alone (Silverstein et al., 1987). Self-administered ergonomic risk assessment tools have been recommended for prevention, alongside interventions such as job rotation, ergonomic education, and workplace modifications (Werner & Armstrong, 1997; Lincoln et al., 2000).

Beyond physical impairment, CTS substantially affects quality of life. Persistent pain, numbness, and hand dysfunction interfere with daily activities, disrupt sleep, and cause frustration, ultimately reducing productivity and well-being (Huisstede et al., 2018). Recent perspectives also suggest that nutrition and nutraceutical approaches may play a role in managing obesity-related risks and improving long-term musculoskeletal health (Amin et al., 2024).

Overall, CTS is a highly prevalent and debilitating neuropathy with both occupational and non-occupational determinants. Understanding its risk

factors, anatomical basis, symptoms, and treatment modalities is essential for effective prevention and management. Given its impact on health, work performance, and quality of life, CTS remains a critical area for clinical and occupational health research.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Carpal Tunnel Syndrome (CTS) is a prevalent occupational and public health concern characterized by compression of the median nerve in the wrist, leading to symptoms such as pain, numbness, tingling, and weakness. Its association with repetitive hand use, awkward wrist positions, and psychosocial stressors makes it particularly common among workers engaged in manual tasks, including hairdressers and barbers. A wide range of studies conducted in different countries have explored CTS prevalence, risk factors, diagnostic methods, and management approaches, providing significant insights into its impact.

Erick et al. (2021) investigated 184 hairstylists in Gaborone using the Boston Carpal Tunnel Syndrome Questionnaire (BCTQ), finding a high prevalence of CTS, particularly among females. The study emphasized that individual, work-related, and psychosocial factors are key contributors. Similarly, Demiryurek and Aksoy Gündoğdu (2018) conducted an interventional study in Turkey using nerve conduction and electromyography tests. Their results showed a higher frequency of CTS among women aged 18–45, with severity strongly associated with repetitive and forceful hand movements. Reduction in working hours was suggested as an effective preventive measure.

In Pakistan, Kamal et al. (2023) examined 49 hairdressers in Lahore, highlighting the frequency of musculoskeletal disorders, while Hesari et al. (2019) reported CTS prevalence among 109 male hairdressers in Iran, with 22 diagnosed cases. Their findings confirmed varying severity levels and recommended workstation adjustments to alleviate symptoms. Another study by Zaheer et al. (2023) on 167 male barbers found musculoskeletal disorders—particularly affecting the neck and lower back—were widespread, underscoring the need for ergonomics training.

The Boston Carpal Tunnel Questionnaire (BCTQ) has been validated as a reliable tool for measuring

symptom severity and functional impairment (Leite et al., 2006). Its use in occupational and clinical studies highlights its importance in standardizing CTS evaluation. Demiryurek and Aksoy Gündoğdu (2018) further compared hairdressers with unemployed women, finding significantly higher CTS prevalence (74.3%) among hairdressers, with longer exposure linked to increased risk and symptom severity.

General population studies also contribute valuable data. De Krom et al. (1992) identified undiagnosed CTS cases among Dutch participants, finding brachialgia paraesthetica nocturna (BPN) to be a useful diagnostic symptom. Similarly, Wright and Atkinson (2019) emphasized early diagnosis and intervention to prevent long-term disability and economic burden. Giersiepen and Spallek (2011) confirmed that repetitive wrist flexion, gripping, and vibration are occupational risks, while typing showed no significant link to CTS.

Diagnostic accuracy has been widely studied. Hems et al. (2009) found questionnaires and clinical tests like Tinel's and Phalen's to have good predictive value, while Szabo et al. (1999) and Gerritsen et al. (2002) highlighted the importance of nerve conduction studies for confirmation. Studies like MacDermid and Wessel (2004) cautioned against unnecessary imaging while reinforcing electrodiagnostic testing as the gold standard.

Several risk factors are identified across occupational and non-occupational settings. Maghsoudipour et al. (2008) reported 11.9% CTS prevalence among Iranian factory workers, linking risk to heavy lifting, smoking, and vibrating tools. Kozak et al. (2015) confirmed dose-response relationships between hand activity and CTS risk, while Gupta and Benstead (1997) stressed the diagnostic value of patient-reported symptoms like nocturnal numbness. Personal health factors such as age, gender, BMI, diabetes, and vitamin D deficiency also increase susceptibility (Lam & Thurston, 1998; Abdul-Razzak & Kofahi, 2020).

In terms of management, physiotherapy is widely recommended. De Krom et al. (1992) and Bobowik (2019) described stretching, tendon gliding, ergonomic correction, and manual therapy as key interventions. Huisstede et al. (2018) reported benefits from modalities such as TENS, ultrasound,

and myofascial release. Conservative treatments—splints, corticosteroids, and ergonomic adjustments—remain first-line, while surgery is reserved for severe or persistent cases (Carlson et al., 2010; Hernández-Secorún et al., 2021). Notably, Gerritsen et al. (2002) emphasized conservative management during pregnancy due to high postpartum resolution rates. Finally, CTS has profound psychosocial and quality-of-life implications. It disrupts sleep, reduces work capacity, and lowers well-being, often causing frustration and emotional distress (Patel et al., 2012; Huisstede et al., 2018). Moreover, studies by Crossman et al. (2001) revealed that CTS patients generally report lower levels of depression and greater pain control compared to those with other chronic non-neurological conditions, suggesting distinct coping mechanisms. Overall, the literature consistently demonstrates that CTS is strongly associated with repetitive occupational tasks, with hairdressers and barbers among the most vulnerable groups. Standardized diagnostic tools, ergonomic interventions, and physiotherapy remain central to management, while

broader strategies addressing individual risk factors and workplace modifications are crucial for prevention.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY DESIGN

A Cross-sectional survey

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Convenient sampling

STUDY DURATION

Data is collected in four months after synopsis.

SAMPLE SIZE

The sample size is calculated via the Open EPI tool. The total population of Rawalpindi and Islamabad between the ages of 18 and 60 is estimated to be around 4,297,698. This is based on data from the 2017 census. In Rawalpindi approximately 2,915,378 people are estimated between age 18 and 60. In Islamabad approximately 1,382,320 people are estimated between age 18 and 60

So, we put the 4,297,698 the total population of Twin Cities in Open EPI tool and we get 385 sample size with 95% confidence level.

Sample Size for Frequency in a Population

Population size(for finite population correction factor or fpc)(N):	4297699
Hypothesized % frequency of outcome factor in the population (p):	50%+/-5
Confidence limits as % of	5%
100(absolute +/- %)(d):	
Design effect (for cluster surveys-1 DEFF):	1
Sample Size(n) for Various Confidence Levels	
Confidence Level(%)	Sample Size
95%	385
80%	165
90%	271
97%	471
99%	664
99.9%	1083
99.99%	1514

Equation

$$\text{Sample size } n = \frac{[DEFF * N * p * (1-p)]}{[(d^2 / Z^2) * (1-p)]}$$

Results from OpenEpi, Version 3, open source calculator--SSPropor
Print from the browser with ctrl-P or select text to copy and paste to other programs.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

Age 18 to 60
Male and Female hairdressers Work load minimum 7 to 10 hours
Working Experience minimum 5 years
Exclusion Criteria Prior Wrist Injury or Surgery
Current Medication Pregnancy
Mental Health Conditions

TOOLS

The tool we used is Boston Carpal Tunnel Syndrome Questionnaire. This tool demonstrated excellent internal consistency reliability as the Cronbach's alpha values ranges from 0.80 to 0.90 for the symptom severity scale and from 0.88 to 0.93 for functional status scale

The Pearson's correlation coefficient for symptom severity scale is from 0.64 to 0.91 and for functional status scale is from 0.71 to 0.93

Its validity has been shown to be high when it was compared with widely used upper extremity patient outcomes whose spear man reliability is from 0.71 to 0.90

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FREQUENCIES

AGE:

Age

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	16-26	101	26.2	26.2	26.2
	27-37	167	43.4	43.4	69.6
	38-48	82	21.3	21.3	90.9
	49-60	34	8.8	8.8	99.7
Total	385		100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.1. shows out of 385 participants 26.2% with frequency of 101 are between age of 16-26, 43.4% with frequency of 167 are between age of 27-37, 21.3% with frequency of 82 are between the age of 38-48 and 8.8% with frequency of 34 are between age of 49-60.

GENDER

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	MALE	194	50.4	50.4	50.4
	FEMALE	191	49.6	49.6	100.0
Total		385	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.2 shows out of 385 participants 50.4% with frequency of 194 are male participants and 49.6% with frequency of 191 are female participants.

WORKING EXPERIENCE:

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	5-15	275	71.4	71.4	71.4
	16-26	90	23.4	23.4	94.8
	27-37	20	5.2	5.2	100.0
	Total	385	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.3 shows working experience of 385 participants and the participants with 5 to 15 years of experience have the frequency of 275 and these are 71.4% , the participants with 16 to 16 years of

experience have the frequency of 90 and these are 23.4%, the participants with 27 to 37 years of

experience have the frequency of 20 and these are 5.2%.

WORKING HOURS

Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 7hrs	28	7.3	7.3
8hrs	127	33.0	40.3
9hrs	63	16.4	56.6
10hrs	167	43.4	100.0
Total	385	100.0	

Table 4.1.4 shows working hours of 385 participants and the participants with 7 hours of working experience have frequency of 28 and these are 7.3%, the participants with 8 hours of working experience have frequency of 127 and these are 33%, the

participants with 9 hours of working experience have frequency of 63 and these are 16.4%, the participants with 10 hours of working experience have frequency of 167 and these are 43.4%.

PAIN AT NIGHT

Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Normal	311	80.8	80.8
Slight	54	14.0	94.8
Medium	18	4.7	99.5
Severe	2	.5	100.0
Total	385	100.0	

Table 4.1.5 shows participants with hand or wrist pain at night. The normal participants were with the frequency of 311 and these are 80.8%. The slight pain participants were with the frequency of 54 and

these are 14%. The participants with medium pain were with the frequency of 18 and these are 4.7%. The participants with severe pain were with the frequency of 2 and these are 0.5%.

DURATION OF PAIN

Duration of pain in hand at night in past two weeks

Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Normal	308	80.0	80.0
Once	41	10.6	90.6
2-3 times	30	7.8	98.4
4-5 times	5	1.3	99.7
More than 5 times	1	.3	100.0
Total	385	100.0	

Table 4.1.6 shows the duration of pain in hand at night in past two weeks. The normal participants were with the frequency of 308 and these were 80.0% . The participants facing pain once were with the frequency of 41 and these are 10.6% . The

participants facing pain 2-3 times were with the frequency of 30 and these are 7.8%. The participants facing pain 4 to 6 times were with the frequency of 5 and these are 1.3% .The participants facing pain

more than 5 times were with the frequency of 1 and these are 0.3%.

PAIN DURING DAYTIME

Pain in hand or wrist during daytime

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No pain	309	80.3	80.3	80.3
	Slight	46	11.9	11.9	92.2
	Medium	24	6.2	6.2	98.4
	Severe	5	1.3	1.3	99.7
	Very serious	1	.3	.3	100.0
	Total	385	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.7 shows the duration of pain in hand during daytime . The normal participants were with the frequency of 309 and these were 80.3% . The participants facing slight pain were with the frequency of 46 and these are 11.9% . The

participants facing medium pain were with the frequency of 24 and these are 6.2%. The participants facing severe pain were with the frequency of 5 and these are 1.3% .The participants facing very serious pain were with the frequency of 1 and these are 0.3%.

DURATION OF PAIN

Duration of pain in hand or wrist during daytime

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Normal	310	80.5	80.5	80.5
	1-2 times a day	52	13.5	13.5	94.0
	3-5 times a day	11	2.9	2.9	96.9
	More than 5 times	5	1.3	1.3	98.2
	Continued	7	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	385	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.8 shows the duration of pain in hand or wrist during daytime . The normal participants were with the frequency of 310 and these were 80.5% . The participants facing pain 1 to 2 times a day were with the frequency of 52 and these are 13.5% . The participants facing pain 3 to 5 times were with the

frequency of 11 and these are 2.9%. The participants facing pain more than times were with the frequency of 5 and these are 1.3% .The participants facing continued pain were with the frequency of 7 and these are 1.8%.

EPISODE OF PAIN

Average episodes of pain last during daytime

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Normal	317	82.3	82.3	82.3
	<10min	29	7.5	7.5	89.9
	10-60 minutes	27	7.0	7.0	96.9
	>60 minutes	4	1.0	1.0	97.9
	Continued	8	2.1	2.1	100.0
	Total	385	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.9 shows the average episodes of pain during daytime . The normal participants were with the frequency of 317 and these were 82.3% . The participants facing pain less than 10 minutes were with the frequency of 29 and these are 7.5% . The participants facing pain 10 to 60 minutes were with

NUMBNESS

Numbness in hand

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Normal	295	76.6	76.6	76.6
	Slight	57	14.8	14.8	91.4
	Medium	28	7.3	7.3	98.7
	Severe	5	1.3	1.3	100.0
	Total	385	100.0	100.0	

the frequency of 27 and these are 7.0%. The participants facing pain more than 60 minutes were with the frequency of 4 and these are 1.0% .The participants facing continued pain were with the frequency of 8 and these are 2.1%.

Table 4.1.10 shows participants with numbness in hand . The normal participants were with the frequency of 295 and these are 76.6% . The slight pain participants were with the frequency of 57 and

WEAKNESS

Weakness in hand or wrist

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Normal	300	77.9	77.9	77.9
	Slight	49	12.7	12.7	90.6
	Medium	30	7.8	7.8	98.4
	Severe	3	.8	.8	99.2
	Very serious	3	.8	.8	100.0
	Total	385	100.0	100.0	

these are 14.8% . The participants with medium pain were with the frequency of 28 and these are 7.3% . The participants with severe pain were with the frequency of 5 and these are 1.3%.

Table 4.1.11 shows participants with weakness in hand or wrist . The normal participants were with the frequency of 300 and these are 77.9% . The slight pain participants were with the frequency of 49 and these are 12.7% . The participants with medium

TINGLING

Tingling Sensation

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Normal	308	80.0	80.0	80.0
	Slight	52	13.5	13.5	93.5
	Medium	19	4.9	4.9	98.4

pain were with the frequency of 30 and these are 7.8% . The participants with severe pain were with the frequency of 3 and these are 0.8%. The participants with very serious pain were with the frequency of 3 and these are 0.8%.

Severe	5	1.3	1.3	99.7
Very serious	1	.3	.3	100.0
Total	385	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.12 shows participants with tingling sensation. The normal participants were with the frequency of 308 and these are 80.0% . The slight pain participants were with the frequency of 52 and these are 13.5% . The participants with medium

pain were with the frequency of 19 and these are 4.9% . The participants with severe pain were with the frequency of 5 and these are 1.3%. The participants with very serious pain were with the frequency of 1 and these are 0.3%.

NUMBNESS OR TINGLING:

Numbness or tingling at night

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Normal	305	79.2	79.2
	Slight	52	13.5	92.7
	Medium	19	4.9	97.7
	Severe	7	1.8	99.5
	Very serious	2	.5	100.0
	Total	385	100.0	100.0

Table 4.1.13 shows participants with numbness and tingling at night . The normal participants were with the frequency of 305 and these are 79.2% . The slight pain participants were with the frequency of 52 and these are 13.5% . The participants with medium

pain were with the frequency of 19 and these are 4.9% . The participants with severe pain were with the frequency of 7 and these are 1.8%. The participants with very serious pain were with the frequency of 2 and these are 0.5%.

NUMBNESS OR TINGLING AT NIGHT:

Numbness or tingling at night during past two weeks

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Normal	316	82.1	82.1
	Once	39	10.1	92.2
	2-3 times	25	6.5	98.7
	Upto 5 times	5	1.3	100.0
	Total	385	100.0	100.0

Table 4.1.14 shows participants with numbness and tingling at night during past two weeks. The normal participants were with the frequency of 316 and these are 82.1% . The participants facing pain once were with the frequency of 39 and these are 10.1% . The

participants facing pain 2 to 3 times were with the frequency of 25 and these are 6.5% . The participants with pain up-to 5 times were with the frequency of 5 and these are 1.3%.

DIFFICULTY IN GRASPING

Difficulty in grasping small objects

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Without difficulty	328	85.2	85.2

Little difficulty	39	10.1	10.1	95.3
Moderate difficulty	12	3.1	3.1	98.4
Very difficult	5	1.3	1.3	99.7
Very difficult	1	.3	.3	100.0
Total	385	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.15 shows participants with difficulty in grasping small objects. The participants without difficulty were with the frequency of 328 and these are 85.2%. The participants little difficulty were with the frequency of 39 and these are 10.1%. The participants with moderate difficulty were with the

frequency of 12 and these are 3.1%. The participants with very difficult were with the frequency of 5 and these are 1.3%. The participants with very severe difficulty were with the frequency of 1 and these were 0.3%.

WRITING

Writing

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No difficulty	334	86.8	86.8
	Little difficulty	39	10.1	96.9
	Moderate difficulty	10	2.6	99.5
	Intense difficulty	2	.5	100.0
	Total	385	100.0	100.0

Table 4.1.16 shows participants with difficulty in writing. The participants without difficulty were with the frequency of 334 and these are 86.8%. The participants little difficulty were with the frequency of 39 and these are 10.1%. The participants with

moderate difficulty were with the frequency of 10 and these are 2.6%. The participants with intense difficulty were with the frequency of 2 and these are 0.5%.

BUTTONING OF CLOTHES

Buttoning of Clothes

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No difficulty	329	85.5	85.5
	Little difficulty	40	10.4	95.8
	Moderate difficulty	12	3.1	99.0
	Intense difficulty	4	1.0	100.0
	Total	385	100.0	100.0

Table 4.1.17 shows participants with difficulty in buttoning of cloths. The participants without difficulty were with the frequency of 329 and these are 85.5%. The participants little difficulty were with

the frequency of 40 and these are 10.4%. The participants with moderate difficulty were with the frequency of 12 and these are 3.1%. The participants

with intense difficulty were with the frequency of 4 and these are 1.0%.

HOLDING A BOOK

Holding a Book while reading

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No difficulty	317	82.3	82.3	82.3
	Little difficulty	48	12.5	12.5	94.8
	Moderate difficulty	16	4.2	4.2	99.0
	Intense difficulty	4	1.0	1.0	100.0
	Total	385	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.18 shows participants with difficulty in holding a book while reading. The participants without difficulty were with the frequency of 317 and these are 82.3%. The participants little difficulty were with the frequency of 48 and these are 12.5%.

The participants with moderate difficulty were with the frequency of 16 and these are 4.2%. The participants with intense difficulty were with the frequency of 4 and these are 1.0%.

GRIPPING OF TELEPHONE

Gripping of Telephone handle

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No difficulty	308	80.0	80.0	80.0
	Little difficulty	57	14.8	14.8	94.8
	Moderate difficulty	17	4.4	4.4	99.2
	Intense difficulty	2	.5	.5	99.7
	Cannot perform activity at all due to symptom	1	.3	.3	100.0
Total		385	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.19 shows participants with difficulty in gripping of telephone handle. The participants without difficulty were with the frequency of 308 and these are 80.0%. The participants little difficulty were with the frequency of 57 and these are 14.8%. The participants with moderate difficulty were with

the frequency of 17 and these are 4.4%. The participants with intense difficulty were with the frequency of 2 and these are 0.5%. The participants who cannot perform activity at all due to symptoms were with the frequency of 1 and these are 0.3%.

OPENING OF JARS

Opening of Jars

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No difficulty	318	82.6	82.6	82.6
	Little difficulty	44	11.4	11.4	94.0
	Moderate difficulty	21	5.5	5.5	99.5

Intense difficulty	2	.5	.5	100.0
Total	385	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.20 shows participants with difficulty in opening of jars. The participants without difficulty were with the frequency of 318 and these are 82.6%. The participants little difficulty were with the frequency of 44 and these are 11.4%. The

participants with moderate difficulty were with the frequency of 21 and these are 5.5%. The participants with intense difficulty were with the frequency of 2 and these are 0.5%.

HOUSEHOLD CHORES:

Household Chores

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No difficulty	329	85.5	85.5
	Little difficulty	41	10.6	96.1
	Moderate difficulty	9	2.3	98.4
	Intense difficulty	5	1.3	99.7
	Cannot perform activity due to symptoms	1	.3	100.0
	Total	385	100.0	100.0

Table 4.1.21 shows participants with difficulty in household chores. The participants without difficulty were with the frequency of 329 and these are 85.5%. The participants little difficulty were with the frequency of 41 and these are 10.6%. The participants with moderate difficulty were with the

frequency of 9 and these are 2.3%. The participants with intense difficulty were with the frequency of 5 and these are 1.3%. The participants who cannot perform activity at all due to symptoms were with the frequency of 1 and these are 0.3%.

CARRYING OF GROCERY BASKETS

Carrying of Grocery Baskets

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No difficulty	321	83.4	83.4
	Little difficulty	43	11.2	94.5
	Moderate difficulty	17	4.4	99.0
	Intense difficulty	4	1.0	100.0
	Total	385	100.0	100.0

Table 4.1.22 shows participants with difficulty in carrying of grocery baskets. The participants without difficulty were with the frequency of 321 and these are 83.4%. The participants little difficulty were with the frequency of 43 and these are 11.2%. The

participants with moderate difficulty were with the frequency of 17 and these are 4.4%. The participants with intense difficulty were with the frequency of 4 and these are 1.0%.

BATHING AND DRESSING

Bathing and Dressing

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No difficulty	336	87.3	87.3	87.3
	Little difficulty	33	8.6	8.6	95.8
	Moderate difficulty	15	3.9	3.9	99.7
	Intsnse difficulty	1	.3	.3	100.0
	Total	385	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.23 shows participants with difficulty in bathing and dressing. The participants without difficulty were with the frequency of 336 and these are 87.3%. The participants little difficulty were with the frequency of 33 and these are 8.6%. The

participants with moderate difficulty were with the frequency of 15 and these are 3.9%. The participants with intense difficulty were with the frequency of 1 and these are 0.3%.

TOTAL SCORING

Total Scoring

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Normal	339	88.1	88.1	88.1
	Mild	39	10.1	10.1	98.2
	Moderate	6	1.6	1.6	99.7
	Severe	1	.3	.3	100.0
	Total	385	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.24 shows total scoring. The participants who are normal were with the frequency of 339 and these are 88.1%. The participants who are mild were with the frequency of 39 and these are 10.1%. The

participants who are moderate were with the frequency of 6 and these are 1.6%. The participants who are severe were with the frequency of 1 and these are 0.3%.

PREVALENCE OF CTS

Prevalence of CTS

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	CTS	46	11.9	11.9	11.9
	NON CTS	339	88.1	88.1	100.0
	Total	385	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.25 shows the prevalence of CTS. Those participants who are suffering CTS were with the frequency of 46 and these are 11.9%. Those

participants who are non CTS were with the frequency of 339 and these are 88.1%.

ASSOCIATIONS

Weakness in hand or wrist and Household Chores

TABLE 4.1.1 ASSOCIATION BETWEEN WEAKNESS AND HOUSEHOLD CHORES

Household Chores

No difficulty		Little difficulty	Moderate difficulty	Intense difficulty	
Weakness in hand or wrist	Normal	293	7	0	0
	Slight	27	20	2	0
	Medium	7	14	5	4
	Severe	2	0	0	1
	Very serious	0	0	2	0
Total		329	41	9	5

TABLE 4.1.2 CHI-SQUARE TEST

Chi-Square Tests

Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	
Pearson Chi-Square	401.536a	16	.000
Likelihood Ratio	179.378	16	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	192.315	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	385		

Table 4.1.1 and 4.1.2: As p-value is <.05 so there is a significant association between the two variables. The minimum expected count is .01.

Weakness in hand or wrist

TINGLING SENSATION AND HOUSEHOLD CHORES

TABLE 4.1.3 ASSOCIATION BETWEEN TINGLING SENSATIONS AND HOUSEHOLD CHORES

Household Chores

		No difficulty	Little difficulty	Moderate difficulty	Intense difficulty
Tingling sensation	Normal	298	10	0	0
	Slight	24	22	6	0
	Medium	7	8	3	1
	Severe	0	1	0	4
	Very serious	0	0	0	0
Total		329	41	9	5

TABLE 4.1.4 CHI-SQUARE TESTS
Chi-Square Tests

Value		df	Asymptotic (2- sided)	Significance
Pearson Chi-Square	777.671a	16	.000	
Likelihood Ratio	171.149	16	.000	
Linear-by-Linear Association	202.374	1	.000	
N of Valid Cases	385			

Table 4.1.3 and 4.1.4: As p-value is <.05 so there is a significant association between the two variables. The minimum expected count is .00.

NUMBNESS IN HAND AND HOUSEHOLD CHORES

TABLE 4.1.5 ASSOCIATION BETWEEN NUMBNESS AND HOUSEHOLD CHORES

Household Chores					
No difficulty		Little difficulty	Moderate difficulty	Intense difficulty	
Numbness in hand	Normal	287	7	0	1
	Slight	34	20	3	0

	Medium	6	14	6	2
	Severe	2	0	0	2
Total		329	41	9	5

TABLE 4.1.6 CHI-SQUARE TEST

Chi-Square Tests

Value	df	Asymptotic (2-sided)	Significance
Pearson Chi-Square	312.720a	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	158.326	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	162.191	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	385		

Table 4.1.5 and 4.1.6: As p-value is $<.05$ so there is a significant association between the two variables. The minimum expected count is .01.

Duration of pain in hand at night in past two weeks and Household Chores Table 4.1.9 Association between pain at night and household chores Household Chores

		No difficulty	Little difficulty	Moderate difficulty
Duration of pain in hand at night in past two weeks	Normal	297	10	0
	Once	25	16	0
	2-3 times	6	15	8
	4-5 times	0	0	1
	More than 5 times	1	0	0
Total		329	41	9

TABLE 4.1.10 CHI-SQUARE TESTS

Chi-Square Tests

Value		df	Asymptotic (2- sided)	Significance
Pearson Chi-Square	420.893a	16	.000	
Likelihood Ratio	176.014	16	.000	
Linear-by-Linear Association	186.569	1	.000	
N of Valid Cases	385			

Table 4.1.9 and 4.1.10: As p-value is <.05 so there is a significant association between the two variables. The minimum expected count is .00.

Duration of pain in hand at night in past two weeks

RESULTS

Table 4.1.1. Shows out of 385 participants 26.2% with frequency of 101 are between age of 27-37, 43.4% with frequency of 167 are between age of 37-47, 21.3% with frequency of 82 are between the age of 38-48 and 8.8% with frequency of 34 are between age of 49-60. Table 4.1.2 shows out of 385 participants 50.4% with frequency of 194 are male participants and 49.6% with frequency of 191 are female participants. Table 4.1.3 shows working experience of 385 participants and the participants with 5 to 15 years of experience have the frequency of 275 and these are 71.4% , the participants with 16 to 16 years of experience have the frequency of 90 and these are 23.4% , the participants with 27 to 37 years of experience have the frequency of 20 and these are 5.2%. Table 4.1.4 shows working hours of 385 participants and the participants with 7 hours of working experience have frequency of 28 and these are 7.3% , the participants with 8 hours of working experience have frequency of 127 and these are 33% , the participants with 9 hours of working experience have frequency of 63 and these are 16.4% , the participants with 10 hours of working experience have frequency of 167 and these are 43.4%. Table 4.1.5 shows participants with hand or wrist pain at

night. The normal participants were with the frequency of 311 and these are 80.8% . The slight pain participants were with the frequency of 54 and these are 14% . The participants with medium pain were with the frequency of 18 and these are 4.7% . The participants with severe pain were with the frequency of 2 and these are 0.5%. Table 4.1.6 shows the duration of pain in hand at night in past two weeks . The normal participants were with the frequency of 308 and these were 80.0% . The participants facing pain once were with the frequency of 41 and these are 10.6% . The participants facing pain 2-3 times were with the frequency of 30 and these are 7.8%. The participants facing pain 4 to 6 times were with the frequency of 5 and these are 1.3% . The participants facing pain more than 5 times were with the frequency of 1 and these are 0.3%. Table 4.1.7 shows the duration of pain in hand during daytime. The normal participants were with the frequency of 309 and these were 80.3% . The participants facing slight pain were with the frequency of 46 and these are 11.9% . The participants facing medium pain were with the frequency of 24 and these are 6.2%. The participants facing severe pain were with the frequency of 5 and these are 1.3% . The participants

facing very serious pain were with the frequency of 1 and these are 0.3%. Table 4.1.8 shows the duration of pain in hand or wrist during daytime. The normal participants were with the frequency of 310 and these were 80.5%. The participants facing pain 1 to 2 times a day were with the frequency of 52 and these are 13.5%. The participants facing pain 3 to 5 times were with the frequency of 11 and these are 2.9%. The participants facing pain more than times were with the frequency of 5 and these are 1.3%. The participants facing continued pain were with the frequency of 7 and these are 1.8%. Table 4.1.9 shows the average episodes of pain during daytime. The normal participants were with the frequency of 317 and these were 82.3%. The participants facing pain less than 10 minutes were with the frequency of 29 and these are 7.5%. The participants facing pain 10 to 60 minutes were with the frequency of 27 and these are 7.0%. The participants facing pain more than 60 minutes were with the frequency of 4 and these are 1.0%. The participants facing continued pain were with the frequency of 8 and these are 2.1%. Table 4.1.10 shows participants with numbness in hand. The normal participants were with the frequency of 295 and these are 76.6%. The slight pain participants were with the frequency of 57 and these are 14.8%. The participants with medium pain were with the frequency of 28 and these are 7.3%. The participants with severe pain were with the frequency of 5 and these are 1.3%. Table 4.1.11 shows participants with weakness in hand or wrist. The normal participants were with the frequency of 300 and these are 77.9%. The slight pain participants were with the frequency of 49 and these are 12.7%. The participants with medium pain were with the frequency of 30 and these are 7.8%. The participants with severe pain were with the frequency of 3 and these are 0.8%.

The participants with very serious pain were with the frequency of 3 and these are 0.8%. Table 4.1.12 shows participants with tingling sensation. The normal participants were with the frequency of 308 and these are 80.0%. The slight pain participants were with the frequency of 52 and these are 13.5%. The participants with medium pain were with the frequency of 19 and these are 4.9%. The participants with severe pain were with the frequency of 5 and these are 1.3%. The participants with very serious

pain were with the frequency of 1 and these are 0.3%. Table 4.1.13 shows participants with numbness and tingling at night. The normal participants were with the frequency of 305 and these are 79.2%. The slight pain participants were with the frequency of 52 and these are 13.5%. The participants with medium pain were with the frequency of 19 and these are 4.9%. The participants with severe pain were with the frequency of 7 and these are 1.8%. The participants with very serious pain were with the frequency of 2 and these are 0.5%. Table 4.1.14 shows participants with numbness and tingling at night during past two weeks. The normal participants were with the frequency of 316 and these are 82.1%. The participants facing pain once were with the frequency of 39 and these are 10.1%. The participants facing pain 2 to 3 times were with the frequency of 25 and these are 6.5%. The participants with pain up-to 5 times were with the frequency of 5 and these are 1.3%. Table 4.1.15 shows participants with difficulty in grasping small objects. The participants without difficulty were with the frequency of 328 and these are 85.2%. The participants with little difficulty were with the frequency of 39 and these are 10.1%. The participants with moderate difficulty were with the frequency of 12 and these are 3.1%. The participants with very difficult were with the frequency of 5 and these are 1.3%. The participants with very severe difficulty were with the frequency of 1 and these were 0.3%. Table 4.1.16 shows participants with difficulty in writing. The participants without difficulty were with the frequency of 334 and these are 86.8%. The participants with little difficulty were with the frequency of 39 and these are 10.1%. The participants with moderate difficulty were with the frequency of 10 and these are 2.6%. The participants with intense difficulty were with the frequency of 2 and these are 0.5%. Table 4.1.17 shows participants with difficulty in buttoning of cloths. The participants without difficulty were with the frequency of 329 and these are 85.5%. The participants with little difficulty were with the frequency of 40 and these are 10.4%. The participants with moderate difficulty were with the frequency of 12 and these are 3.1%. The participants with intense difficulty were with the frequency of 4 and these are 1.0%. Table 4.1.18 shows participants with difficulty in holding a book while reading. The

participants without difficulty were with the frequency of 317 and these are 82.3% . The participants little difficulty were with the frequency of 48 and these are 12.5%. The participants with moderate difficulty were with the frequency of 16 and these are 4.2%. The participants with intense difficulty were with the frequency of 4 and these are 1.0%.Table 4.1.19 shows participants with difficulty in gripping of telephone handle . The participants without difficulty were with the frequency of 308 and these are 80.0% . The participants little difficulty were with the frequency of 57 and these are 14.8%. The participants with moderate difficulty were with the frequency of 17 and these are 4.4%. The participants with intense difficulty were with the frequency of 2 and these are 0.5%. The participants who cannot perform activity at all due to symptoms were with the frequency of 1 and these are 0.3%.Table 4.1.20 shows participants with difficulty in opening of jars . The participants without difficulty were with the frequency of 318 and these are 82.6% . The participants little difficulty were with the frequency of 44 and these are 11.4%. The participants with moderate difficulty were with the frequency of 21 and these are 5.5%. The participants with intense difficulty were with the frequency of 2 and these are 0.5%. Table 4.1.21 shows participants with difficulty in household chores. The participants without difficulty were with the frequency of 329 and these are 85.5% . The participants little difficulty were with the frequency of 41 and these are 10.6% . The participants with moderate difficulty were with the frequency of 9 and these are 2.3%. The participants with intense difficulty were with the frequency of 5 and these are 1.3%. The participants who cannot perform activity at all due to symptoms were with the frequency of 1 and these are 0.3%.Table 4.1.22 shows participants with difficulty in carrying of grocery baskets. The participants without difficulty were with the frequency of 321 and these are 83.4% . The participants little difficulty were with the frequency of 43 and these are 11.2%. The participants with moderate difficulty were with the frequency of 17 and these are 4.4%. The participants with intense difficulty were with the frequency of 4 and these are 1.0%. Table 4.1.23 shows participants with difficulty in bathing and dressing . The participants without difficulty were

with the frequency of 336 and these are 87.3% . The participants little difficulty were with the frequency of 33 and these are 8.6%. The participants with moderate difficulty were with the frequency of 15 and these are 3.9%. The participants with intense difficulty were with the frequency of 1 and these are 0.3%.Table 4.1.24 shows total scoring . The participants who are normal were with the frequency of 339 and these are 88.1%. The participants who are mild were with the frequency of 39 and these are 10.1%. The participants who are moderate were with the frequency of 6 and these are 1.6%. The participants who are severe were with the frequency of 1 and these are 0.3%. Table 4.1.25 shows the prevalence of CTS . Those participants who are suffering CTS were with the frequency of 46 and these are 11.9%. Those participants who are non CTS were with the frequency of 339 and these are 88.1%.

DISCUSSION

In this research, data is collected from 385 hairdressers in Rawalpindi and Islamabad. Among those the participants only 46 (11.9%) were diagnosed Carpal Tunnel Syndrome(CTS) on the basis of symptoms and functional tests.Meanwhile, 339 (88.1%) participants have shown no symptoms of Carpal Tunnel Syndrome . Boston Carpal Tunnel Syndrome Questionnaire , Phalen's test and Tinel sign were conducted to obtained data from the hairdressers. This comprises of the symptoms severity scale and functional limitations scale. This study has collected data from both males and females hairdressers, 194 (50.4%) out of 385 were male hairdressers and 191 (49.6%) out of 385 were female hairdressers. The study shows that the participants with no symptoms of CTS have the frequency of 339 and these are 88.1% . The participants with mild CTS symptoms have the frequency of 39 and these are 10.1%. The participants with moderate symptoms of CTS have the frequency of 6 out of 385 and these are 1.6%. The participants with severe CTS symptoms were have the frequency of only 1 out of 385 and these are 0.3%.The study concluded that there is only one individual with the severe symptoms of CTS , only 6 Individuals out of 385 with moderate symptoms of CTS and 39 individuals were with the frequency of mild CTS which shows

that CTS is a concerning condition among hairdressers in twin cities Rawalpindi and Islamabad. A study conducted in Gaborone suggests the high prevalence of CTS among female hairdressers (Erick et al., 2021). A study conducted in Turkey high prevalence of CTS among male hairdressers (Demiryurek & Aksoy Gündoğdu, 2018). A study conducted in Iran among 109 male hairdressers shows that 10 had mild, 7 had moderate and 5 had severe CTS symptoms (Hesari et al., 2019).

LIMITATIONS

One of the main limitations is the potential for recall bias due to the self-reported nature of Carpal Tunnel Syndrome (CTS) symptoms. Some participants were not entirely clear or confident about the presence of specific symptoms when responding to the questionnaire. Additionally, since the data was collected through self-reporting, there may have been misinterpretation or under-reporting of symptoms. Another limitation is related to time constraints. A period of four months was given after the approval of our synopsis, which was relatively short for collecting data from a large sample of 385 hairdressers. Furthermore, the educational background of most participants (mainly matriculate or intermediate level, with only a few being graduates) also posed challenges during data collection, as some participants found it difficult to fully understand certain questions despite our efforts to explain them. Future studies in the twin cities should explore ergonomic factors and workplace modifications for hairdressers to better understand and address the risk of CTS.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings indicate that Carpal Tunnel Syndrome is a noticeable occupational health concern among hairdressers, with a prevalence rate of 11.9%. Despite long working hours and repetitive hand use, most participants reported mild or no symptoms. However, a subset experienced functional limitations that could affect job performance and quality of life. These results emphasize the need for preventive strategies, such as ergonomic training, regular breaks, and early screening, to minimize CTS risk and maintain work efficiency among hairdressers. Future research could explore the effectiveness of these interventions.

REFERENCES

- Abdul-Razzak, K. K., & Kofahi, R. M. (2020). Carpal tunnel syndrome: A link with vitamin D and calcium. *Biomed Rep*, 13(3), 15. <https://doi.org/10.3892/br.2020.1322>
- Aboonq, M. S. (2015). Pathophysiology of carpal tunnel syndrome. *Neurosciences Journal*, 20(1), 04-09. <https://nsj.org.sa/content/nsj/20/1/04.full.pdf>
- Amin, R., Alam, F., Kemisetti, D., Sarkar, D., & Dey, B. K. (2024). Carpal Tunnel Syndrome Management by Nutraceuticals. In *Nutraceuticals and Bone Health* (pp. 205-219). Apple Academic Press.
- Berlanga-de-Mingo, D., Lobo-Escolar, L., López-Moreno, I., & Bosch-Aguilá, M. (2019). Association between multiple trigger fingers, systemic diseases and carpal tunnel syndrome: A multivariate analysis. *Revista Española de Cirugía Ortopédica y Traumatología (English Edition)*, 63(4), 307-312.
- Bobowik, P. Ž. (2019). Effectiveness of physiotherapy in carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS) [journal article]. *Advances in Rehabilitation*, 33(2), 47-58. <https://doi.org/10.5114/areh.2019.85023>
- Carlson, H., Colbert, A., Frydl, J., Arnall, E., Elliot, M., & Carlson, N. (2010). Current options for nonsurgical management of carpal tunnel syndrome. *International journal of clinical rheumatology*, 5(1), 129.
- The Carpal Tunnel Syndrome: Diagnostic Utility of the History and Physical Examination Findings. (1990). *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 112(5), 321-327. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-112-5-321> %m 2306060
- Crossman, M. W., Gilbert, C. A., Travlos, A., Craig, K. D., & Eisen, A. (2001). Nonneurologic Hand Pain Versus Carpal Tunnel Syndrome: Do Psychological Measures Differentiate? *American Journal of Physical Medicine & Rehabilitation*, 80(2), 100-107. https://journals.lww.com/ajpmr/fulltext/2001/02000/nonneurologic_hand_pain_ver_sus_carpal_tunnel.4.aspx
- Dada, S., Burger, M. C., Massij, F., de Wet, H., & Collins, M. (2016). Carpal tunnel syndrome:

- The role of collagen gene variants. *Gene*, 587(1), 53-58.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gene.2016.04.030>
- de Krom, M. C., Knipschild, P. G., Kester, A. D., Thijs, C. T., Boekkooi, P. F., & Spaans, F. (1992). Carpal tunnel syndrome: prevalence in the general population. *J Clin Epidemiol*, 45(4), 373-376. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356\(92\)90038-o](https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356(92)90038-o)
- De Krom, M. C. T. F. M., Knipschild, P. G., Kester, A. D. M., Thijs, C. T., Boekkooi, P. F., & Spaans, F. (1992). Carpal tunnel syndrome: Prevalence in the general population. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 45(4), 373-376. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356\(92\)90038-O](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356(92)90038-O)
- Demiryurek, B. E., & Aksoy Gündoğdu, A. (2018). Prevalence of carpal tunnel syndrome and its correlation with pain amongst female hairdressers. *Int J Occup Med Environ Health*, 31(3), 333-339. <https://doi.org/10.13075/ijomeh.1896.01068>
- Durkan, J. A. (1991). A new diagnostic test for carpal tunnel syndrome. *JBJS*, 73(4), 535-538. https://journals.lww.com/jbjsjournal/fulltext/1991/73040/a_new_diagnostic_test_for_carpal_tunnel_syndrome_9.aspx
- Erick, P., Benjamin, K., Raditloko, S., Tapera, R., & Mbongwe, B. (2021). Risk factors for self-reported carpal tunnel syndrome among hairstylists in Gaborone, Botswana. *Int J Occup Med Environ Health*, 34(3), 437-450. <https://doi.org/10.13075/ijomeh.1896.01659>
- Genova, A., Dix, O., Saefan, A., Thakur, M., & Hassan, A. (2020). Carpal Tunnel Syndrome: A Review of Literature. *Cureus*, 12(3), e7333. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.7333>
- Genova, A., Dix, O., Saefan, A., Thakur, M., Hassan, A., & Arguello, M. T. (2020). Carpal tunnel syndrome: a review of literature. *Cureus*, 12(3).
- Gerritsen, A. A., De Krom, M. C., Struijs, M. A., Scholten, R. J., De Vet, H. C., & Bouter, L. M. (2002). Conservative treatment options for carpal tunnel syndrome: a systematic review of randomised controlled trials. *Journal of neurology*, 249, 272-280.
- Gerritsen, A. A. M., de Krom, M. C. T. F. M., Struijs, M. A., Scholten, R. J. P. M., de Vet, H. C. W., & Bouter, L. M. (2002). Conservative treatment options for carpal tunnel syndrome: a systematic review of randomised controlled trials. *Journal of neurology*, 249(3), 272-280. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s004150200004>
- Giersiepen, K., & Spallek, M. (2011). Carpal tunnel syndrome as an occupational disease. *Dtsch Arztebl Int*, 108(14), 238-242. <https://doi.org/10.3238/arztebl.2011.0238>
- Gupta, S. K., & Benstead, T. J. (1997). Symptoms experienced by patients with carpal tunnel syndrome. *Canadian journal of neurological sciences*, 24(4), 338-342.
- Gupta, S. K., & Benstead, T. J. (1997). Symptoms experienced by patients with carpal tunnel syndrome. *Can J Neurol Sci*, 24(4), 338-342. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0317167100033023>
- Hems, T. E., Miller, R., Massraf, A., & Green, J. (2009). Assessment of a diagnostic questionnaire and protocol for management of carpal tunnel syndrome. *J Hand Surg Eur Vol*, 34(5), 665-670. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1753193409105566>
- Herbert, R., Gerr, F., & Dropkin, J. (2000). Clinical evaluation and management of work-related carpal tunnel syndrome. *American Journal of Industrial Medicine*, 37(1), 62-74. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-0274\(200001\)37:1<62::AID-AJIM6>3.0.CO;2-D](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0274(200001)37:1<62::AID-AJIM6>3.0.CO;2-D)
- Hernández-Secortín, M., Montaña-Cortés, R., Hidalgo-García, C., Rodríguez-Sanz, J., Corral-de-Toro, J., Monti-Ballano, S., Hamam-Alcober, S., Tricás-Moreno, J. M., & Lucha-López, M. O. (2021). Effectiveness of Conservative Treatment According to Severity and Systemic Disease in Carpal Tunnel Syndrome: A Systematic Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(5), 2365. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/18/5/2365>
- Hesari, A., Kamali, A., & Tavakoli, M. (2019). The Prevalence of Carpal Tunnel Syndrome among Male Hairdressers in Bojnourd, Iran. *Journal of Sport Biomechanics*, 5, 82-91. <https://doi.org/10.32598/biomechanics.5.2.1>

- Huisstede, B. M., Hoogvliet, P., Franke, T. P., Randsdorp, M. S., & Koes, B. W. (2018). Carpal tunnel syndrome: effectiveness of physical therapy and electrophysical modalities. An updated systematic review of randomized controlled trials. *Archives of physical medicine and rehabilitation*, 99(8), 1623-1634. e1623.
<https://doi.org/10.2174/1874325001206010069>
- Ibrahim, I., Khan, W. S., Goddard, N., & Smitham, P. (2012). Carpal tunnel syndrome: a review of the recent literature. *Open Orthop J*, 6, 69-76.
<https://doi.org/10.2174/1874325001206010069>
- Kamal, F., Gillani, M. H. Z., Nawaz, A., Aman, Z., Waseem, A., & Anwar, A. (2023). Frequency of Musculoskeletal Disorders among Hairdressers; A Cross-Sectional Study: Musculoskeletal Disorders among Hairdressers. *The Healer Journal of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation Sciences*, 3(5), 540-548.
- Kao, S. Y. (2003). Carpal Tunnel Syndrome As an Occupational Disease. *The Journal of the American Board of Family Practice*, 16(6), 533.
<https://doi.org/10.3122/jabfm.16.6.533>
- Kouyoumdjian, J. A. (1999). Carpal tunnel syndrome: age, nerve conduction severity and duration of symptomatology. *Arquivos de neuro-psiquiatria*, 57, 382-386.
- Kozak, A., Schedlbauer, G., Wirth, T., Euler, U., Westermann, C., & Nienhaus, A. (2015). Association between work-related biomechanical risk factors and the occurrence of carpal tunnel syndrome: an overview of systematic reviews and a meta-analysis of current research. *BMC musculoskeletal disorders*, 16, 1-19.
- Kozak, A., Schedlbauer, G., Wirth, T., Euler, U., Westermann, C., & Nienhaus, A. (2015). Association between work-related biomechanical risk factors and the occurrence of carpal tunnel syndrome: an overview of systematic reviews and a meta-analysis of current research. *BMC Musculoskeletal Disord*, 16, 231.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12891-015-0685-0>
- Lam, N., & Thurston, A. (1998). Association of obesity, gender, age and occupation with carpal tunnel syndrome. *Australian and New Zealand journal of surgery*, 68(3), 190-193.
- Leite, J. C., Jerosch-Herold, C., & Song, F. (2006). A systematic review of the psychometric properties of the Boston Carpal Tunnel Questionnaire. *BMC Musculoskeletal Disord*, 7, 78.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2474-7-78>
- Lincoln, A. E., Vernick, J. S., Ogaitis, S., Smith, G. S., Mitchell, C. S., & Agnew, J. (2000). Interventions for the primary prevention of work-related carpal tunnel syndrome. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 18(4), 37-50.
- MacDermid, J. C., & Wessel, J. (2004). Clinical diagnosis of carpal tunnel syndrome: a systematic review. *Journal of hand therapy*, 17(2), 309-319.
- Maghsoudipour, M., Moghimi, S., Dehghaan, F., & Rahimpanah, A. (2008). Association of occupational and non-occupational risk factors with the prevalence of work related carpal tunnel syndrome. *J Occup Rehabil*, 18(2), 152-156.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10926-008-9125-4>
- McDiarmid, M., Oliver, M., Ruser, J., & Gucer, P. (2000). Male and female rate differences in carpal tunnel syndrome injuries: personal attributes or job tasks? *Environmental research*, 83(1), 23-32.
- Melhorn, J. M. (1994). CTD: carpal tunnel syndrome, the facts and myths. *Kansas medicine : the journal of the Kansas Medical Society*, 95(9), 189-192.
<http://europemc.org/abstract/MED/7996737>
- Patel, J. N., McCabe, S. J., & Myers, J. (2012). Characteristics of sleep disturbance in patients with carpal tunnel syndrome. *Hand*, 7(1), 55-58.
- Silverstein, B. A., Fine, L. J., & Armstrong, T. J. (1987). Occupational factors and carpal tunnel syndrome. *American Journal of Industrial Medicine*, 11(3), 343-358.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/ajim.4700110310>
- Szabo, R. M., Slater Jr, R. R., Farver, T. B., Stanton, D. B., & Sharman, W. K. (1999). The value of diagnostic testing in carpal tunnel syndrome. *The Journal of hand surgery*, 24(4), 704-714.
- Trillos-Chacón, M.-C., Castillo-M, J. A., Tolosa-Guzman, I., Sánchez Medina, A. F., & Ballesteros, S. M. (2021). Strategies for the prevention of carpal tunnel syndrome in the

- workplace: A systematic review. *Applied Ergonomics*, 93, 103353.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2020.103353>
- Werner, R. A., & Armstrong, T. J. (1997). Carpal tunnel syndrome: ergonomic risk factors and intracarpal. *physical medicine and rehabilitation clinics of North America*, 8(3), 555-569.
- Wright, A. R., & Atkinson, R. E. (2019). Carpal Tunnel Syndrome: An Update for the Primary Care Physician. *Hawaii J Health Soc Welf*, 78(11 Suppl 2), 6-10.
- Zaheer, A., Ayub, A., & Ramzan, O. (2023). Frequency of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders among Barbers. *Journal Riphah College of Rehabilitation Sciences*, 11(02).

